

A SURVEY ON THE PROBLEM OF MARKET UNAWARENESS BETWEEN WHOLESALERS AND RETAILERS.

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this paper is to give details about the survey we carried out in different markets, on the problem of wholesaler and retailer market unawareness, which involves ignorance about favorable prices and location of wholesalers by retailers then also wholesalers lacking more information about their retailers. It gives the Introduction of our survey, background of the study, problem statement, objectives, scope, the significance of the study, design of our survey, design of our data collection instrument, data analysis and processing, related work, recommendation, conclusion, references and appendices.

1 INTRODUCTION

[1]In the market sector of Uganda today, Retailers buy goods from wholesalers so as to sell them to customers in pieces.

Retailers get to know about wholesaler's prices and location by asking brokers who sometimes don't provide enough information, this leads to buying goods at a higher price compared to other wholesalers with lower prices.

wholesalers find it difficult to update all their customers because they send brokers who don't exhaust all their customers, sometimes they use phone calls where by the customers don't pick up, sometimes they pick up but tend not to recognize the real person (wholesaler) they are talking to.

Therefore, we suggest to solve this problem so as to enable retailers know where to go and buy from easily and also wholesaler keep in touch with their retailers.

1.1 Background of The Study

The problem originates from the marketing sector of Uganda among retailers and wholesalers. Retailers get information about prices of goods of wholesalers by asking brokers, asking directly from wholesalers, asking fellow retailers, use phone calls of which that information may be valid or invalid thus making retailers buy goods at unfavorable prices.

The problem covers retailers and wholesalers.

1.2 Problem Statement

Retailers buy goods at unfavorable prices from some wholesalers in the market, due to ignorance about the favorable prices from other wholesalers. According to the current situation, retailers ask brokers about prices of different wholesalers, since these brokers are not well informed about the prices of all wholesalers in the market, they give retailers inadequate information about prices of wholesalers. Hence buying goods at unfavorable prices which could lead to losses.

Wholesalers get to know about their retailers by calling them of which sometimes they fail to pick up or not to recognize them. This limits them from making retailers aware of their services and changes.

Wholesalers find it hard to know how they are performing in market, that is to say knowing their customers and knowing what to stock most. This is because some of them do not capture them. Some may keep a list of their contacts and then loose it. Which makes their customers loose out on new interesting stock.

Retailers find it hard to locate new and already existing wholesalers due to ignorance about their locations. Therefore, it is difficult for wholesalers to always update all their customer about market changes like new prices, new stock and many more, because most of them cannot exhaust all the lists of their contacts.

The problem covers retailers and wholesalers.

The existing solutions do not actually specify all the requirements the wholesalers and the retailers need. It limits the scope to retailers and customers and does not include all issues retailers and wholesalers face. Our solution rectifies these issues by linking wholesalers to retailers hence solving the issues above.

1.3 Objectives

1.3.1 Main Objective

To investigate how retailers, get to know about the prices and locations of different wholesalers in a specific market.

1.3.2 Other Objectives

- To ask wholesalers how they inform retailers about their prices.
- To ask wholesalers on how they inform retailers about other changes like when they change location, when they change stock details and many more.
- To ask retailers how they get to know about the locations of wholesalers.
- To ask retailers how they get to know about the wholesalers in market.
- To ask retailers how they get to know about favorable prices of wholesalers.
- To ask both wholesalers and retailers if they have smart phones.
- To ask retailers some of the challenges they face in locating wholesalers and finding their prices.
- To ask both retailers and wholesalers if an IT solution will be of importance in solving that problem.
- To ask both wholesalers and retailers how they get to know about new wholesalers in the market.
- To ask wholesalers the difficulties they find in making customers get to know about their prices and new products.
- To ask retailers how they get to know about the price changes of products of different wholesalers?
- To ask wholesalers how they get to know about the most products they sell in market.
- To ask wholesalers how they get to know about their customers.

1.4 Scope

The study investigates how retailers get to know about the prices and location of different wholesalers and the challenges they face in that. On the other hand, how wholesalers communicate effectively with their customers.

1.5 Significance of The Study

The significance of this research is to find out how retailers get to know about the prices and locations of different wholesalers, to ask wholesalers how they get to know more about their customers and how they communicate effectively with them, to get requirements of the new solution and also to ask them if an IT solution will be of importance to them.

2 RELATED WORK

[2]According to the previous studies, Prisync is a website that makes price tracking with a perfect accuracy of hundreds of thousands of products in thousands of websites, they keep their customers in peak in price competition, anytime. They offer online price-tracking services to e-commerce website owners and suppliers that operate in more than 40 countries and more than 100 categories. But they don't enable customers locate market. This is how it works.

You add your products and competitor's URL to dashboard, then Prisync tracks availability information of every product and URL you added, then it monitors the details of every products prices and stock availabilities in the dashboard. It is a nice site but it does not enable user locate market, compare prices of products in accordance to distance. So, our research gap is to include market location in our app, price comparison in accordance to distance, and analysis like about new wholesalers in the market.

The sites and apps viewed don't cover all the functionalities we need to add in our price tracer application system. Some focus on comparing prices, but don't mind market location.

Their scope is customers and retailers mainly. They also don't consider comparison of distance in regards to location.

3 RESEARCH METHOD

[1] Survey methods where we used interview guides.

4 DESIGNS OF OUR SURVEY

4.1 Data collection:

[1] The data collection method we used was an interview. It was a structured interview with open-ended questions.

4.2 The Data Collection Tools were:

- Interview guide
- Pen
- Notebook
- Recorder

4.3 Data processing:

The data processing method we used was a narrative analysis method.

4.4 Target population.

Retailers and wholesalers in different places like, wandegeya, kikuubo, mini price, etc.

4.5 Sample size

The sample size was 60 wholesalers and retailers. We randomly selected 15 wholesalers and retailers from different market places. We chose 4 places that is to say wandegeya, kikuubo, mini-price, and mukwano arcade. These were appropriate because almost all wholesalers and retailers in different places were giving us almost similar views. Hence sample was generalizable.

4.6 Sample method

The sampling type we used was Cluster sampling, under the probability sampling strategy. That is to say random selection. We used it because we didn't have lists of all wholesalers and retailers.

5 Design of Our Data Collection Instrument

[3]Below is the interview guide we used during data collection. The types of questions we asked were open ended-questions.

INTERVIEW GUIDE FOR PRICE TRACER APPLICATION.

1. Introduction

- Greeting the interviewee.
- Introducing the rest of the selection team and explaining our collection roles.
- Clarifying how much time is available and explaining the next stages of the process.

2. Warm up questions

- How is the day?
- How is the business going?

3. Main body

WHOLESELLER

- 1) How do you get to know your customers?
- 2) How do you communicate with your customers?
- 3) How do your customers get to know about your prices?
- 4) What difficulties do you face in making them get to know about your prices?
- 5) What other means do you think would help out in making people get to know about prices?
- 6) Do you think an application can help out?
- 7) How do you think a mobile application can help you out in making your customers get to know about your prices?
- 8) Do you have a smart phone?
- 9) How do you get to know about other whole sellers' prices?

RETAILERS

- 1) How do you get to know the location of your wholesaler?
- 2) Who are your wholesalers?
- 3) How do you get to know about different wholesalers' prices of your products?
- 4) How do you get to know about new wholesalers in the market?
- 5) How do you get to know the wholesaler with a favorable price for your product?
- 6) How do you determine which wholesaler to go to?
- 7) Do you find any problem in determining which wholesaler to buy from?
- 8) Do you think an application can work out?
- 9) How do you think a mobile application can help you out in determining which supplier to buy from?
- 10) Do you have a smart phone?
- 11) How do you get to know about the price changes of different wholesalers?

4 Wrap up.

Tell us more about how you think determining which wholesaler to buy from can be changed?

Figure 1 shows interview guide

6 DATA ANALYSIS AND PROCESSING

[1] After collecting data, we studied the notes we made during the interview, and identified common views wholesalers and retailers have about the problem, and they are as follows:

6.1 Views on how wholesalers inform retailers about their prices.

The following are some of the views we got about the above point:

- Through calling them.
- Through sending them messages.
- Sending brokers to inform them.
- Through Facebook.
- Through WhatsApp.

Figure 2 shows analysis of wholesalers

Among the wholesalers interviewed about this, 33% said through calling them, 20% said through sending messages, 23% said sending brokers to inform them, 7% said through Facebook, and 17% through WhatsApp.

6.2 Views on how retailers get to know about the locations of wholesalers.

- Asking other retailers.
- Asking brokers.
- Wholesalers themselves inform.
- Business cards.
- Through phone calls.
- Research using phones

Figure 3 shows analysis of retailers

Among the retailers interviewed, 33% of them said asking other retailers, 20% said asking brokers, 10% said wholesalers themselves inform them, 13% said through business cards, 17% said through phone calls, 7% research using phones.

6.3 Views on how retailers get to know about favorable prices of wholesalers.

- Through moving through all wholesalers, asking them about their prices of a specific products and then compare.
- Buying from different wholesalers such that to know about their prices Asking other retailers.
- Asking brokers.

Figure 4 shows analysis

Among retailers interviewed about this, 40% said through moving through all wholesalers, 13% said buying from different wholesalers, 27% said asking other retailers, 20% said asking brokers.

6.4 Views on whether both wholesalers and retailers have smart phones.

- Yes
- No

Figure 5 shows a number wholesaler with smart phones

Among the interviewees, 85% of them said they have smart phone and 15% of them said they do not have smart phones.

6.5 Views on challenges faced by retailers in locating and finding prices of wholesalers.

- Time consuming
- Tiresome
- Expenses
- Unbudgeted expenses

Figure 6 shows graph of challenges

Among the retailers interviewed about this, 37% said its time consuming, 50% said its tiresome, and 13% said unbudgeted expenses.

6.6 Views on whether an IT solution will be of importance in solving that problem.

- It will be very important
- It will be useful.
- It will not be useful.

Figure 7 shows a number of wholesalers and retailers

According to the analysis made, we found out that, 27% said it will be very important, 60% said it will be fine and 4% said it will not be useful.

6.7 Views on how retailers get to know about new wholesalers in the market.

- Wholesalers move around themselves informing the retailers.
- By observation, as they are buying their products they tend to find new wholesalers in the market.
- From fellow retailers
- Through sign posts
- Adverts

Figure 8 shows another an analysis

According to the analysis made 20% said through wholesalers moving around them, 30% said through observation, 17% said through asking fellow retailers, 13% said through sign posts,10% said through business cards, 7% said through radio adverts and 3% said through television adverts.

6.8 Views on how retailers get to know about the price changes of products of different wholesalers?

- Asking brokers.
- Get to know price changes during buying good.

Figure 9 shows the number of retailers

According to the analysis made, 30% of the retailer said by asking brokers, 50% of them said during purchase of goods and 20% of them said through phone calls.

6.8 Views on how retailers compare prices?

- Common sense

For example, if a product is cheaper but the wholesaler is far compared to the product which is a bit expensive but the wholesaler is near

Figure 10 shows how retailers compare prices

According to the analysis made, 67% of the retailers use common sense and 33% use calculating prices on paper after noting them down.

7 CONCLUSIONS

7.1 Aim

The aim of our research was to really understand the problem, find the best solution to the problem, through understanding requirements. To find if the users will like the solution which is an IT solution.

7.2 Was the aim achieved?

The aim was achieved because we were able to get the information we wanted.

7.3 Challenges encountered during data collection.

- It was so tiresome.
- Time consuming. Some of the retailers and wholesalers could first work on customers and then come back to us.
- We could fear some people who looked tough.
- Language barrier.
- Some interviewees could not give us their time.
- Product of the research.
- The product of our research was the IT solution requirements.

8 RECOMMENDATIONS

According to our analysis about this problem, we recommend an IT solution by developing a mobile application because a bigger percentage of the interviewees were positive about it and also had smart phone. This will help retailers in locating wholesalers, determine wholesalers with favorable prices, notify retailers about the changes in prices, knowing the new wholesalers in the market and also do the comparisons of the different prices and distances of wholesalers.

9 FUTURE WORK

- Documenting the requirements specification document basing on the requirements collected.
- Documenting the design document basing on the requirements specification document.
- Application implementation basing on the design document and specification document.
- Testing the application product.
- Deploying the application.
- Maintaining the system.

10 REFERENCES

[1] "OLX," [Online]. Available: www.olx.co.ug.

[2] "5 steps to create Good user interview questions," [Online]. Available: www.@metacole.com.

[3] N. Birley, in *a practical guide to academic research*, 1998.

11 APPENDICES

11.1 The interview guide is shown above in section 9.

11.2 Attached are audio recording captured during the interview.

11.3 These are some of the notes we took during the interview.

Figure 11 shows a list of our notations

11.4 These are the photos we took during the interview

